

ROLL-TO-ROLL MANUFACTURING OF CARBON NANOTUBE FORESTS ON METAL FOILS

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1. Introduction

For large-scale synthesis of carbon nanotube (CNT) powders, floating catalyst CVD using fluidized bed reactors has enabled worldwide production capacity to exceed several thousand tons per year [1, 2]. However, the scalable manufacturing of organized CNTs remains at a relative infancy. Specifically, the widespread potential applications of vertically aligned carbon nanotubes ("CNT forests") have stimulated recent work on large-area chemical vapor deposition (CVD) growth methods, because many potential devices and interfaces utilizing CNT forests cannot bear the cost and limited area of batch-style processing on silicon wafers. Within academia, multiple large-scale static CVD systems have been developed recently for growth of CNT forests and graphene [3, 4], along with dynamic roll-to-roll (R2R) systems [5, 6], but issues with quality, uniformity, and consistency still present problems for commercial integration. Rapid growth of the flexible electronics and composites markets is creating further need for efficient, continuous CVD processing machines and methods.

Moreover, to enable engineering of CNT forests to achieve desired mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties, a priori control of the catalyst diameter and density is needed. Therefore, a most attractive continuous process for CNT forest manufacturing would couple a scalable catalyst deposition process, which enables control of catalyst particle size and packing density, with an efficient R2R CVD process that accommodates flexible substrates including metal foils and advanced fibers. Metallic substrates enable flexibility along with electrical and thermal

conductivity for CNT forest applications such as interconnects, supercapacitors, and heat spreaders.

While the floating catalyst (e.g., aerosol) method has been used to deposit particles on metal foils to in turn enable CNT forest growth [7, 8], typically an oxide or "support" layer is also required between the substrate and the catalyst. Electron charge donation between the support layer and the catalyst particles has been identified as the primary factor for the need of the support layer, and direct evidence of its impact on the growth of CNT forests has been documented [9, 10]. Among the various oxide layers to choose from, alumina (Al₂O₃) has been consistently shown as one of the most beneficial materials. In addition, alumina's chemical structure creates a diffusion barrier that slows the catalyst migration into the substrate. Deposition methods for the alumina layer have included dip coating, e-beam evaporation, and native surface oxidation of aluminum [11–13]. Using these methods prior to catalyst deposition, metal ribbons including Ni, Cu, Ta and various others have been shown to produce CNT forests [11, 14–16], but CNT height is limited when compared to typical results on Si substrates. Additionally, although it would seem that the oxide layer would limit conductivity between the CNTs and the metallic substrate, recent work has shown that < 10nm thin films of alumina can both support growth and still allow electrical conduction to the substrate [17].

Recently, several studies have focused on larger area CNT forest growth, but much of this work focused on batch processing of rigid substrates, not continuous flexible substrates. In 2002, Jiang et al.,

began creating super-aligned CNT forests (composed of MWNTs) for the creation of spun CNT yarns and fibers [18], which was later scaled up to 4" (2004) and 8" (2008) diameter wafers [19] using low-pressure CVD (LP-CVD) systems. In 2009, Yasuda et al. combined several techniques such as water injection and gas delivery using a top-down showerhead approach into a furnace system that resulted in the largest areal growth of CNT forests known to date [3]. This process reported a carbon efficiency of 32% (vs. ~ 1% for typical lateral flow systems) and produced SWNT forests that covered substrate areas as large as an A4 sheet of paper, with uniform height over the area of ~1 mm. Recently, Yasuda et al. have reported growth on 0.5 x 0.5 m rigid substrates using a pilot assembly line that produces CNT forests at a rate of 100 g/hr. Towards a continuous process, Guzmán de Villoria et al. continuously feed discrete substrates through a furnace as a step towards R2R processing, where individual Si substrate samples were fed through a custom CVD furnace using a conveyor belt approach [5].

Focusing on flexible substrates, R2R processing is especially attractive from a manufacturing standpoint because it enables continuous substrates to be used, and the CVD treatment times are directly controlled by the substrate feed rate. Additionally, flexible substrates have been processed using kinematic web handling techniques, creating a large industrial experience base from which to draw upon.

We present a continuous process and bench-scale prototype machines that couple each of the processing steps for CNT forest synthesis. We use a convective self-assembly process for the deposition of an oxide support layer and uniform layers of catalyst particles, along with a novel R2R CVD furnace. Together, these enable the synthesis of CNT forests on flexible metal foils and woven fibers, and each process technology is compatible and scalable to large areas and potentially high speeds.

2. Approach

The ultimate goal for R2R manufacturing of CNT forests is to create a fully integrated system that incorporates each of the key processing steps (Fig. 1). The processing steps of interest are catalyst

deposition, substrate annealing, CNT growth, and CNT delamination with optional transfer. The catalyst deposition involves either a thin film or pre-formed particles of a suitable catalyst material such as Fe or Ni (or reducible oxides of such). Reduction of the catalyst into its native metallic state is the primary purpose of the substrate annealing step, but this step also provides the necessary parameters to enable a thin film catalyst to undergo dewetting and form particles suitable for CNT growth. With metallic catalyst particles on the substrate, a carbon feedstock gas is introduced into the CVD system and CNTs are nucleated and grow from the catalyst particles. Through mechanical interactions, the CNTs vertically align and form the CNT forest structure. Because the growth substrate is not always suitable for the intended application of CNT forests, the forest can be mechanically cleaved or transferred to a secondary substrate after the growth process. Naturally, each step must be able to handle similar substrate materials, web sizes, and processing speeds. Because the processing speed is most directly linked with the system throughput, the individual processing steps for the growth of CNT forests must either occur at the same speed, or each zone must be sized such that the translating substrate remains in the treatment zone for the appropriate amount of time. Finally, because either the gas composition and/or temperature are unique to each processing step, zone decoupling must also be taken into account when designing a R2R system for CNT forest growth.

Two prototype desktop R2R machines were created for the deposition of support and catalyst layers, and for the growth of CNT forests on flexible substrates. The continuous catalyst machine (CCM) (Fig. 2a, b) uniformly applies a nanoparticle solution that, after evaporation of the solvent, results in an array of catalyst nanoparticles whose density is determined by the particle concentration and deposition speed. This substrate is then fed into the continuous growth machine (CGM) (Fig. 2c-e), which utilizes a unique CVD reactor design for annealing and CNT growth [20].

Using the CCM, an alumina sol. as described by Dorfler et al. [11] is first deposited on a flexible metal substrate using a continuous convective assembly process to create a support layer for CNT growth. The substrate is then allowed to rest in air

to allow the solvents to evaporate, and this is folled by a low temperature annealing step in He to form a uniform support layer. Then, using the same machine, catalyst particles are then deposited from a solution of commercially available iron oxide nanoparticles. The solution meniscus is pinned between the curved “blade” edge and the flexible substrate. Tuning of the assembly parameters enables control of particle packing as described by Dimitrov et al. [21]

$$v_c = \frac{\beta l j_e \varphi}{h(1-\varepsilon)(1-\varphi)}. \quad (1)$$

Here β is a coefficient of proportionality, j_e is the volumetric evaporation flux per unit area of the solvent, l is the evaporation length, φ is the particle volume fraction in the suspension, h is the thickness of the layer, and ε is the porosity of the array. In order to maintain a steady growth rate of a particle monolayer, the relative motion speed (v_r) must equal v_c . If $v_r > v_c$, a non-close-packed particle layer will be formed, whereas if $v_r < v_c$, multiple particle layers will be formed. CNT forest density and diameter are also subsequently controlled through this catalyst deposition process, as we have previously demonstrated on silicon substrates [22].

After catalyst deposition, the catalyst-coated foil feeds into the R2R CVD furnace, CGM, which utilizes a novel concentric tube design. The thin foil substrate, wrapped in a helical path around the inner tube, continuously translates (by motorized tension from the output reel) and is exposed to the gas atmosphere in the small uniform gap between the concentric tubes (Fig. 2). Radial holes in the inner tube sidewall allow for a carbon precursor gas to be introduced at a specific location in the heated region, which enables tuning of the CNT growth kinetics based on gas decomposition [23]. This design enables the catalyst annealing and CNT growth atmospheres to be seamlessly combined in a seamless single-zone thermal environment. Further, compared to a conventional tube furnace, the concentric tube CVD system enables a feed gas volume savings of over 90% using standard quartz tube sizes, at the same average gas velocity.

3. Results

Copper (Cu) foil 6 mm wide and 50 μm thick (H. Cross Company, 99.99% purity) was used as the flexible substrate for CNT forest growth via the

process described above. The alumina sol. [11] was deposited at a rate of 1 mm/s using the continuous deposition machine (Fig. 2). The substrates remained in air at room temperature for 5 min to allow the bulk of the solvent to evaporate, which was followed by a 5 min anneal at 300 C in He. Next, an isopropyl alcohol based ferrofluid (Ferrotec NF3263L) was deposited on the substrate at a rate of 0.5 mm/s using the continuous deposition machine. The particle diameter was 32.2 ± 12.0 nm as measured by DLS. Prior to installation of the substrate in the CGM, the substrates remained in air at room temperature for 10 min to ensure that all of the solvent evaporated.

Results gleaned from previous growth results on Cu and Si substrates [22, 24] indicated an exposure of the substrate to the annealing and growth zones for 10 min each was desired. Thus, the feed-rate of the substrate was set to 15 mm/min. A 13 mm OD tube was used as the inner concentric tube with a standard 25 mm OD x 23 mm ID outer tube. The tube furnace used was a Lindberg Blue M (25 mm diameter x 30 cm heated zone) and the growth zone flowrates were set to 260/65/65 (sccm) He/H₂/C₂H₄ respectively. The furnace temperature was also set to 775 C which included the annealing and growth zones. Following previous findings from Futaba et al. [25], the water concentration within the CVD system was controlled to 150 ppm using an oxygen injection technique [26]. This method includes injecting small amounts of O₂ diluted in He (0.5-1.0% O₂) directly into the furnace with the annealing and growth gases (pure He flow rates are adjusted to maintain a constant total flow in the reactor). At the elevated temperature within the furnace the O₂ reacts with the H₂ and forms H₂O which is monitored by a hygrometer downstream of the CVD reactor. This method offers a more simplistic gas plumbing configuration and a more responsive system than a typical H₂O bubbler configuration.

Growth of CNTs on Cu substrates yielded significantly different results as compared to Si based substrates using the same reactant mixture and moisture level. Although the standard recipe stated above resulted in CNT forest height of approximately 1 mm on Fe/Al₂O₃/SiO₂/Si, the same parameters yielded either no CNT growth or sparse tangled CNT mats on the Cu substrates (Fig. 3). Several attempts using adjusted oxide and catalyst

deposition parameters, along with different growth gas flow rates yielded similarly unsuccessful findings, relative to the goal of CNT forest growth. However, when the H₂O content in the system was significantly increased to levels approaching 1500 ppm, the samples generated short (5 μm) aligned CNT forests over the entire sample (Fig. 3). Interestingly, this CNT forest has a highly aligned top surface with a minimal tangled crust which suggests that these samples would provide good mechanical contact to a mating surface (Fig. 3c). This morphology has the potential for high electrical and thermal conductivity as well.

The correlation between CNT forest growth on Cu and H₂O content was shown to be consistent over several trials; lower H₂O levels (10-500 ppm) produced sparse tangled CNT growth and higher H₂O levels (1500 ppm) yielded aligned forest growth. Although H₂O has been suggested to increase catalyst yield by etching the amorphous carbon from the catalyst [27], our findings suggest that the H₂O is having a cooperative effect with the Al₂O₃ layer generated by the sol. or the Cu substrate itself. We are studying this in further depth.

Last, we demonstrate the utility of our R2R CVD system for continuous CNT forest growth on ceramic fibers. In general, ceramic fibers are flexible and able to withstand high temperatures, can support CNT growth without additional oxide depositions, and do not experience hydrogen embrittlement as do some metallic substrates. However, as with glass and carbon fibers, proper understanding of fiber heat treatment is needed to preserve the mechanical properties of the fibers. CNT growth on the fibers occurs normal to the surface, which creates a "fuzzy" or "mohawk" fiber, enabling additional mechanical interaction between fibers in a woven mat [28–30]. CNT growth on pre-woven fabrics can then be infiltrated with resin to create composite materials having additional strength due to CNT delamination during peeling and fiber "pull-out." Recently, Applied Nanostructured Solutions, LLC reported the commercialization of CNT forest growth on glass fibers [31].

In this study, a 1/8" diameter woven sleeve of Nextel ceramic fibers (Omega, XC-18) was coated with the same catalyst particles (Ferrotec NF3263L, 32.2 ±

12.0 nm diameter) through the wicking action of droplets placed on the surface, which is easily compatible with continuous processing. Using the growth parameters described above, with a H₂O content of 150 ppm, the substrate was fed through the R2R CVD reactor at a rate of 33 mm/min. Fig. 4 illustrates the radial CNT forest growth from the individual fiber surfaces. CNT forest growth on the Nextel fibers displayed localized forest heights of ~100 μm. The localized curvature of the ceramic fibers splits the forest into "blades" similar to previous studies [29, 32, 33].

Finally, we note that both the metal foil and ceramic fiber growth experiments were terminated prior to the portion of the substrate with CNT forests reaching the take-up roller. Undoubtedly the winding and layering of these materials on the take-up roller would negatively affect the CNT forest structure, thus the material would have to go directly to a post-processing step to either encase the CNTs in a protective layer, or transfer them to a desired substrate. Further work on CNT-foil and CNT-fiber adhesion is also needed.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, we have demonstrated the ability to grow CNT forests on both Cu and woven ceramic substrates using a set of R2R prototype machines for material deposition and CVD processing. CNT forest growth on Cu substrates using an Al₂O₃ sol. support layer and preformed catalyst particles exhibited a need for H₂O content 10 times that of optimal growth on typical Si substrates. Future integration of the R2R deposition process with the concentric tube CVD reactor will enable seamless production of CNT forests on metallic foils for use in applications such as supercapacitors, interconnects and heat spreaders, and possibly on a variety of advanced fibers for composite material applications.

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Fig. 1. Schematic of CNT forest growth steps.

Fig. 2. Sequential R2R machine modules for nanoparticle monolayer deposition and CNT growth. a) Schematic of catalyst particle deposition using convective assembly [22], b) Continuous deposition machine that combines R2R processing with convective assembly, c) Schematic of the concentric tube CVD reactor, d) Cross section schematic of the concentric tube CVD reactor, and e) Prototype benchtop concentric tube CVD reactor.

Fig. 3. CNT growth on flexible Cu substrates. a) Photograph of the Cu substrate translating out of the furnace with a CNT forest where catalyst particles were deposited, b) SEM images of tangled CNTs grown on a Cu substrate where the H₂O content was 150 ppm, and c) SEM images of a CNT forest grown on a Cu substrate where the H₂O content was 1500 ppm.

Fig. 4. CNT forest growth on woven Nextel ceramic fiber sleeve. a) Photograph of the ceramic fiber sleeve translating out of the furnace with CNT forest growth, b) SEM image of the CNT forests growth on several fibers, c) Magnified SEM image of a single ceramic fiber with CNT forest growth from the sample in (a & b).